

Figure S1. The number of functional entities (FE) along the SEPC. The blue line (\pm Interval confidence of 5% and 95%) is the LOESS regression through the data point estimated with an alpha 0.2.

Figure S2. Taxonomic and functional indices estimated to each biogeographical region (tropical, warm and cold) contrasting the differences among regions with a Kruskal-Wallis test ($H = \text{Chi}^2$; $p = \text{probability}$). (a) Species richness. (b) Functional Entities (FE) (c) Functional diversity (RaoQ). (d) Functional richness (FRic). (e) Functional redundancy (FRed). (f) Functional evenness (FEve). (g) Functional specialization (FSpe). (h) β -taxonomic diversity (β_T) and β -functional diversity (β_F).

Figure S3. Pattern of community-weighted mean (CWM) trait values of marine invertebrates along the SEPC. Latitudinal change patterns of traits can be grouped into four responses. Of 31 traits, 23% clearly decrease its weigh with latitude, while 35% of the traits tend to increase poleward. Traits such as pelagic, fast, predation, grazing, register peaks between 0-10°S, to later decrease towards pole. While traits weights such as infaunal, interference/defence (Fighth), deposit feeders, solitary life forms, and body sizes >50mm, despite its variability, tends to increase only between 20-40°S. These results show the presence of gradual replacement of traits that gradually modifies the functional composition along SEPC (see also, Fig. 4, Fig. S7, and SIMPER Table S2).

Figure S4. Residual-diagnostic graphs for random forest model. The first column summarized the relationship between observed and predicted for each variable. The second column reports the latitudinal distribution of standardized residuals, whilst the third column shows the spatial autocorrelogram of the residuals. (Gray line ± 95 interval confidence of the null model).

Figure S5. Partial dependence plots extracted from the Random Forest analysis. Each graph represents the mean marginal influence of each predictor on the species richness and FD facets along the SEPC. Each plot represents the effect of each range variable while holding the other variables constant. The predictors of each row were sorted, from highest to lowest, considering their relative effect on the biological variables. There is no area range, however the area variable is included to maintain the standard of the analyses.